

BEARING FAILURE OF COMPOSITE PINNED JOINTS USING PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE MODELING

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ABSTRACT

An analytical investigation was performed to study the damage in a laminated composite plate containing a pinned joint and subjected to in-plane loading. The objective of this investigation was to understand the fundamental failure mechanisms resulting from stress concentrations in the plate. The technique of progressive damage modeling was used during the investigation to predict the extent and failure modes of the internal damage in the laminate as a function of applied load. The model is capable of predicting the three major in-plane failure mechanisms inherent to the problem, which are: net tension failure, shear-out, and bearing failure. In particular the bearing failure mode is modeled with a new approach.

The model gives insight into the failure of pinned joints, showing how the load and mode of failure are affected by geometry, ply layup sequence, and material changes. A nonlinear finite element analysis exists, based on the model which can be used as a tool for designing with composite components containing pinned joints. The computer code predicts the failure modes and extent of internal damage in the laminates as a function of the applied load and simulates the in-plane response of the laminates from initial loading to final collapse

KEYWORDS: failure criterion; pinned joints; damage accumulation; finite element analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Confidence in the use of advanced laminated composite materials in the aerospace industry has prompted the use of such composites in increasingly sophisticated components. As a consequence, areas of analytical investigation are becoming equally sophisticated. One such area is that of the failure analysis of composite pinned joints. Joints are methods used to attach two composite parts together or to attach a metal structure to a composite structure, usually by means of a pin or a bolt. If such a structure is then subjected to in-plane loading, then failure is likely to initiate in the vicinity of the pinned joint, where stress concentrations may be highest. The presence of several modes of failure makes accurate prediction of failure difficult for the designer and thus excessive safety factors are often used.

An understanding and an ability to describe the mechanisms involved in the failure of such joints in composite materials is of paramount importance to the aircraft and aerospace industry. As composites come into more frequent use as stress-critical parts and primary structure, the need for detailed failure analysis becomes increasingly important.

The number of investigators conducting research into the pinned joint problem is extensive [1-10]. Even the earliest investigators saw the need for using finite element methods to establish stress distributions such as Waszczak & Cruse [1] in 1971, but failure analyses at this time were less developed. Agarwal [2] & Soni [3] also used two-dimensional finite element methods. They used an average stress criterion and a tensor polynomial failure criterion respectively. Further investigators relied more on experiments, with Collings [4] who derived equations for predicting the ultimate bearing strength of constrained pin-loaded holes by using a semi-empirical approach, and Kretsis & Matthews [5] who studied the effects of width, edge distance, hole size, bolt clamping pressure and stacking sequence for G.F.R.P. & C.F.R.P., experimentally. Certain investigators, such as De Jong [6] and Eriksson [7] examined the important aspect of pin/hole interface modeling. Chang et al [8] presented a method for predicting the failure strength and failure mode of mechanically fastened fiber reinforced composite laminates and then developed their method for materials exhibiting nonlinearly elastic behavior [9]. Further development led to a progressive damage model for bolted joints in laminated composites, Chang & Chang [10]. This model considered just tension and shear out mode, and did not consider the bearing mode of failure.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider a laminated composite plate with a pin-loaded hole subjected to in-plane loading (see Figure 1). The ply orientation of the laminate can be selected arbitrarily, but it must be symmetric with respect to the middle plane of the plate. The load is applied uniformly at one end of the composite plate and is opposed by a rigid pin which fits the hole, with zero clearance between the hole and the pin. No out-of-plane loading, bending or torsion is applied. Failure may occur anywhere in the plate but usually initiates at stress concentrations (pin/hole contact surface) at critical load levels.

The load is applied incrementally and the plate is allowed to deform in its own plane until it cannot sustain any additional load. It is desired to find:

1. initiation of damage,
2. load, and location of damage propagation,
3. final failure mode.

3. METHOD OF APPROACH

The model developed for analyzing the pinned joint problem is based on previous work [11,12], where the analysis of compression failure of an open-holed composite plate was performed. In this work, the primary objective is to model failure in laminated composites due to in-plane material damage, rather than out-of-plane buckling. Also, since out-of-plane bolt loading is not considered, the problem becomes that of two-dimensional plane stress.

3.1 Stress analysis

The stress analysis is a two-dimensional finite element analysis with the composite nature of the problem handled by laminated composite plate theory. In addition, there are two important nonlinearities which are accounted for by the formulation. The first is the inclusion of material nonlinearity, which is important for the accurate representation of shear stresses.

It is well known [13] that for certain composite layups, marked nonlinearity is shown in their shear stress to shear strain relationship, thus if the proposed model is to accurately predict failure for an arbitrary given layup then this nonlinearity should be included. The second nonlinearity is the inclusion of geometric nonlinearity or "large deformation theory". This is accomplished with the use of an Updated Lagrangian formulation [14]. Large deformations become important at a local level, when failure in certain regions of the finite element mesh causes extensive element distortion.

3.2 Failure analysis The failure analysis is the major concern of the current work. The failure prediction philosophy is to segregate the modes of failure according to the modes that are observed during experiments. For the pinned joint configuration, the following failure modes are deemed important to the solution of the problem:

1. matrix tensile failure
2. matrix compression failure
3. shearing failure between fibers and matrix
4. fiber compression or bearing failure

For each of these modes of failure, a failure criterion is proposed which will predict failure in that mode. The chosen failure criterion are polynomial failure criterion, first proposed by Hashin [15], and modified by the author to take into account the nonlinear behaviour of the material [11]. The failure criterion are applied at the ply level, and will decide which regions of the composite plate will fail and in which mode. For each of the four failure criterion, there exists a corresponding property degradation rule which will determine the degree of material property reduction in the areas of damage. These property degradation rules determine the residual stiffness in areas of damage, and are strongly dependent on the mode of failure involved.

Examples of failure criterion and property degradation rules can be found in [11]. Three of the failure modes, matrix tensile failure, matrix compression, and fiber/matrix shearing use the same failure criterion and property degradation rule, as these modes of failure appear to be present in both the open-holed compression problem and the pinned joint problem. As an example, the matrix tensile cracking failure mode has the following form [11]:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_y}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \frac{\frac{\sigma_{xy}^2}{2G_{xy}} + \frac{3}{4}\alpha\sigma_{xy}^4}{S_c^2 + \frac{3}{4}\alpha S_c^4} > I \quad (1)$$

where σ_y ($\sigma_y > 0$) and σ_{xy} are the transverse tensile stress and shear stress in each layer, respectively. Y_t is the transverse tensile strength, S_c is the ply shear strength, G_{xy} is the ply in-plane shear modulus, and α is the shear material nonlinearity parameter [11]. Note that for laminates with linear elastic behaviour ($\alpha=0$), this equation can be reduced to:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_y}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{xy}}{S_c}\right)^2 > I \quad (2)$$

which is the two-dimensional form of the tensile matrix criterion proposed by Hashin [15]. Upon failure in this mode, an appropriate property degradation rule is applied to layers of elements which have failed. The rule is applied to the 3x3 in plane stiffness matrix [11]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & \frac{E_y\nu_y}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & 0 \\ \frac{E_y\nu_x}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & \frac{E_y}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} E_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Similar rules exist for matrix compression failure and fiber/matrix shearing. The criterion and property degradation rules can be found in [11].

The bearing failure mode is being modeled with a newly proposed method. First, it is assumed that the initiation of bearing failure may occur in a similar manner to compressive failure of fibers as proposed by Hashin [15] and others. The polynomial failure criterion has the following form:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{X_c}\right)^2 > 1 \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_x < 0$, which is to say that compression failure will occur when the fiber stress, σ_x reaches the compression strength, X_c . This is straightforward, but the difficulty lies in what happens in the post-failure region of the bearing zone. As crushing is occurring at the pin/hole interface, the material is no longer behaving as a well-defined laminated composite material, but rather as a "pseudo-homogeneous" crushed region. Failure continues to propagate with increased load as this crush zone is seen to extend, thus it is assumed that this damaged area can still transfer load. Initially it seems reasonable to modify elements that have been damaged (satisfying equation 4) by reducing their fiber direction property to zero. In the finite element formulation, what happens is that the failed elements ahead of the rigid pin in the crush zone continue to deform until a numerical instability occurs and the program is forced to stop. To avoid this, instead of reducing the material properties of these elements upon failure, the properties are magnified thus making the failed material "incompressible" and allowing the stresses to be transferred to the next row of elements. This process continues with increasing load and eventually a well-defined bearing zone is established. Thus, upon bearing failure, the property change proceeds as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & \frac{E_y\nu_y}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & 0 \\ \frac{E_y\nu_x}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & \frac{E_y}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \frac{10E_x}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & \frac{10E_y\nu_y}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & 0 \\ \frac{10E_y\nu_x}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & \frac{10E_y}{1-\nu_x\nu_y} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 10G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

3.3 Implementation The stress analysis and failure analysis were implemented into a finite element code. In the incremental procedure, the stresses and strains are calculated at each step, and evaluated by the failure criteria to determine

failure occurrences. Mechanical properties are reduced according to the mode of failure by the property degradation models. Stresses and strains are then recalculated to determine any additional damage resulting from the stress redistribution at the same load. This procedure continues until no additional damage is found and the next increment is then pursued. The numerical procedure uses an incremental displacement procedure rather than incremental loading because near final failure of the plate the overall stiffness matrix approaches zero, thus a specified load increment cannot always be attained. The pin is modeled using a radial displacement method, rather than a cosine load distribution to accurately depict the pin behaviour. An overview of the finite element model with boundary conditions is shown in Figure 2.

4. RESULTS

The following ply orientations were chosen as examples to display some of the capabilities of the model:

1. [0/90]_s, a cross-ply laminate,
2. [0/+45/-45/90]_s, a quasi-istropic laminate,
3. [+45/-45]_s, an angle-ply laminate.

Each of the ply layups will be examined separately. The first layup under consideration is the cross-ply laminate. For the specific geometry chosen, $W/D = 4$ (refer to Figure 1), the final failure mode is that of shear-out failure as can be seen in Figure 3. Damage initiated at the hole edge, primarily in the fiber/matrix shearing mode in both layers. Eventually this damage spread along a line in the loading direction in the classic shear-out mode, reaching the top edge of the sample. Some bearing mode failure was also observed ahead of the pin.

The [0/+45/-45/90]_s or quasi-istropic laminate was examined for two geometries in Figures 4 and 5. Figure 4 shows the $W/D=2$ case which depicts a long thin sample. This example is characterized by some bearing damage ahead of the pin load, and extensive matrix tension failure in the 90° layer which reaches the edge to the side of the hole. This is an example of a net tension failure. The sample used in Figure 5 is much wider, $W/D=6$, and results in a failure mode which is primarily in bearing mode. The matrix tension failure in the 90° layer does not have the chance to develop before sizeable bearing failure has occurred at the pin/hole interface.

The [+45/-45]_s laminate is an example of a mixed mode failure, shown in Figure 6. Although the program stopped before damage propagated to an edge, the mode of failure developed into two distinct ways: bearing and net-tension modes. The bearing can be seen at the top of the hole, while the right of the hole shows extensive matrix tension and fiber/matrix shearing modes.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study of failure of a laminated composite plate with a hole filled by a rigid pin and subjected to in-plane loading has been developed using a progressive damage model. The results show how the model can predict the final failure mode for a given ply orientation, and the chosen layups depicted failure in all three of the known mechanisms of failure: bearing, net-tension, and shear-out.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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7. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Basic problem, showing loading and zero clearance pin.

Figure 2. Finite element representation of the problem, showing boundary conditions.

Figure 3. Damage in a [0/90]_s layup, showing shearout mode of failure

